

**EXPERIMENTAL DEVELOPMENT WORK
MONOLOGUE SPEECH OF OLDER CHILDREN
PRESCHOOL AGE IN THE PROCESS OF STORYTELLING**

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Annotation: the article discusses the features of the development of monological speech of older preschool children. The results of experimental work to identify the current level of development of monological speech in older preschool children are shown. The criteria (composition of the utterance, content, grammatical correctness of sentence construction, a variety of ways of communication between sentences, a variety of lexical means, sound design of the utterance), indicators and levels of development of coherent speech of older preschool children (high, medium, low) are determined, diagnostic tools are selected and adapted. The results of the work at the ascertaining stage of the study are presented.

Keywords: monologue speech, diagnostics, criteria, indicators, levels of development of monologue speech, storytelling, older preschool children.

INTRODUCTION

The development of coherent monological speech is the central task of speech education of children. This is primarily due to its social significance and role in the

formation of personality. It is in coherent speech that the main, communicative, function of language and speech is realized. To teach a child to tell it means to form his coherent speech. This task is included as a component in the general task of speech development of preschool children. The researchers note that the development of the ability to tell stories in the preschool period is one of the main components in the psychological examination of a child's readiness for school, and therefore is the most urgent task of the development of modern children.

The problem of developing the ability to tell in preschoolers is reflected in the works of such famous teachers as E.I. Tikheeva, F.A. Sokhin, G.M. Lyamin, O.S. Ushakov, N.F. Ladygin. The patterns of speech development of preschoolers were studied by A.N. Gvozdev, L.S. Vygotsky, D.B. Elkonin, A.A. Leontiev and others. And such issues as the development of coherent speech of preschool children are considered in detail in the works of M.S. Lavrik, T.A. Ladyzhenskaya, F.A. Sokhin, A.M. Borodich, T.B. Filicheva, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the methodology, traditionally, the term "story" is used to denote monologues of various types independently created by children (description, narration, reasoning).

In the older group, children master the structural design of various types of statements: narratives (the beginning of an event, its development and the end), descriptions (thesis, naming the object, characteristics of essential and secondary features, the final evaluation phrase), reasoning (the definition of what is explained or proved, the explanation or proof itself). Two groups of older preschool children were selected for the study: Group A and Group B in the number of 40 children. Teachers of a preschool educational institution also took part in the experimental work. The analysis of the subject-spatial environment has shown that favorable conditions have been created in groups for independent speech activity of children:

various types of theater, plot-role-playing games, viewing fiction, drawing up their own models for description, laying out a series of plot pictures in the correct sequence and composing stories based on them are widely used.

The whole subject-developing environment of the group is organized with the aim of developing children's activity, including speech. The environment satisfies the interests of the children of the group and corresponds to their age and individual characteristics. During direct educational activities for the development of monologue speech, the work is carried out both frontally and with subgroups of children. The direct educational activity on speech development includes the compilation of various stories-descriptions, retellings, stories from personal experience, creative storytelling, etc., as well as work with the families of pupils.

Criteria and indicators for assessing the development of monological speech in the process of storytelling were determined by us based on the content of the preschool program in the line of speech development (development of monological competence).

Based on theoretical research, the study of the tasks of the basic general education program of preschool education "From birth to school", we have identified the following criteria and indicators:

- a variety of ways of connections between sentences – the ability to use methods of formal-compositional communication;
- a variety of lexical means – the ability to use different parts of speech, figurative words-definitions, comparisons, synonyms, antonyms;
- sound design of the utterance – the ability to present the text smoothly, with intonation expressiveness, at a moderate pace.

For the experimental study, we chose the methods with the help of which we determined the level of development of monological speech of older preschool children (high, medium, low). Diagnostic tasks were modified and adapted in accordance with the age of children and consisted of six tasks aimed at identifying

the indicators of the development of monological speech of older preschool children that we identified (Diagnostic task No. 1 "Describe the hedgehog" (O.S. Ushakova, E.M. Strunina); Task No. 2 "Sort out in order" (O.S. Ushakova, E.M. Strunina); Diagnostic task No. 3 "Make up a story" (V.P. Glukhov); Diagnostic task No. 4 "Repeat after the pattern" (T.B. Filicheva); Task No. 5 "Pick up and name" (modification of the methodology O.S. Ushakova, E.M. Strunina); Diagnostic task No. 6 "Tell me with an expression" (V.P. Glukhov)).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data on the formation of indicators of the development of monological speech in older preschool children, obtained according to all the criteria we have identified for the development of monological speech during group and individual examinations they show that children in both groups have relatively similar characteristics, the subject-spatial environment and educational programs are identical, most children correspond to the average level of development of monologue speech. But, despite the work of teachers, there are children with a low level of development of monologue speech. Thus, the number of children in Group A who are at a high level of development of monologue speech is absent, and in Group B they are represented as 20% of children (4 people). At the average level, 65% (13 people) are in Group A, and 60% (12 people) are in Group B, respectively. At a low level of development of monologue speech, as a result of the diagnosis, 35% of children in Group A (7 people), 20% of children in Group B (4 people) were identified.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we see our further work in the development and testing of a set of methodological measures, provided an integrated approach to learning through joint activities, as well as the use of individual work techniques aimed at developing

the monological speech of older preschool children in the process of storytelling.

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